

Gender-Based Differences in Social Adjustment among Upper Basic Students in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research explores gender variations in social adjustment among Upper Basic students in Delta State, Nigeria, with emphasis on the contribution of social studies teachers' interpersonal skills and self-awareness. Drawing on behaviourist and symbolic interactionist perspectives, the study adopted a correlational survey design to investigate how teachers' emotional competence relates to students' social behaviour. The study population comprised Basic Eight (JSS2) learners and their social studies teachers in selected public schools across the state. A stratified random sampling method was applied to choose eight schools from six Local Government Areas, ensuring balance in terms of senatorial districts, school setting (urban/rural), and gender distribution. Data were collected using a validated structured questionnaire, reviewed by experts and pilot-tested for reliability. Analytical procedures included descriptive statistics, Pearson's product-moment correlation, and multiple regression analysis. Findings showed that gender by itself did not exert a significant effect on students' social adjustment. Nevertheless, a combined influence of teachers' social skills, self-awareness, gender, and school location significantly predicted students' adjustment outcomes. The study underscores the critical role of teachers' emotional intelligence in fostering adolescent behavioural adaptation within the school system. It concludes that students' social adjustment is best explained through an interplay of teacher competence, gender dynamics, and contextual factors. Accordingly, it recommends embedding emotional intelligence development into teacher education curricula, particularly for social studies educators. The study provides useful insights for policymakers, teacher trainers, school managers, and counsellors concerned with enhancing social development among secondary school learners in Nigeria.

Keywords: Social adjustment, Emotional intelligence, Gender differences, Delta State

Introduction

The future of any nation is heavily dependent on the quality of its educational system, which is fundamentally driven by the competence and effectiveness of its teachers (Babalola, 2017). Teachers not only deliver academic instruction but also shape

students' behavioural, emotional, and social development. Despite the growing number of teachers in Nigeria's educational sector, there remains a pervasive concern regarding students' poor social adjustment in schools, particularly in public secondary schools across Delta State. Social adjustment, which encompasses a student's ability to interact effectively with peers, adapt to school environments, and manage emotions, is an essential determinant of academic success and psychological well-being. The growing number of academic failures, school dropouts, and cases of truancy, especially among upper basic students, raises critical questions about the underlying factors influencing these behaviours. Scholars have consistently pointed to poor teacher quality, especially a deficiency in emotional intelligence components such as social skills and self-awareness, as a major contributing factor (Okoro, 2020; Marginson, 2021). Social Studies teachers are uniquely positioned to support students' adjustment due to the nature of the subject, which addresses societal values, human relationships, and citizenship. However, the absence of adequate training in social-emotional competencies hinders teachers from effectively fostering positive adjustment among students. Emotional and behavioural problems among students, such as truancy, absenteeism, and disruptive behaviours, have been linked to teachers' lack of social competence and inability to manage classroom relationships effectively (Ubogu, 2022; Emore, 2021).

The significance of this study lies in its potential to provide valuable insights for a broad range of educational stakeholders, including teachers, parents, policymakers, and guidance counsellors, by highlighting the critical role that social-emotional competencies play in shaping students' ability to adjust within the school environment. By examining the complex interplay of factors such as teachers' social skills, students' self-awareness, gender, and school location, the study underscores the need for a more holistic approach to education—one that goes beyond academics to address the emotional and interpersonal development of learners. For teachers in particular, the findings offer practical implications by emphasising the importance of adopting differentiated instructional strategies that are sensitive to the emotional and behavioural diversity present in the classroom. Teachers can use this knowledge to create more inclusive and supportive learning environments where all students, regardless of background or personal challenges, feel valued and understood. These strategies may include the incorporation of social-emotional learning (SEL) activities, the use of positive reinforcement, and the fostering of open communication to enhance student engagement and well-being. Furthermore, the study serves as a call to action for parents and carers to collaborate more closely with schools in nurturing students' social competencies at home and in the community. For policymakers, the findings reinforce the importance of integrating SEL programmes into the curriculum and providing ongoing professional development for educators. Finally, guidance counsellors can draw upon the study to design more targeted interventions that support students at risk of poor social adjustment, ensuring that each child has the opportunity to thrive both socially and academically.

Similarly, the findings will guide parents to create more supportive home environments and encourage policymakers to design effective in-service training for social studies educators (Okorodudu and Okorodudu, 2019). This study is delimited to eight selected public schools drawn from six Local Government Areas, strategically chosen to represent the three senatorial districts of Delta State. The focus is on social studies teachers and students within the upper basic level, specifically targeting Basic Eight (JSS2) classes. By concentrating on this particular educational level and subject area, the research seeks to gain a deeper understanding of gender-based differences in students' social adjustment. Furthermore, it investigates how teachers' social skills and levels of self-awareness may influence or mediate these differences. This focused scope allows for a more nuanced and context-specific analysis, ensuring that the findings are both relevant and applicable within the Delta State educational system.

Objectives of the Study

This study was guided by the following objectives:

- i. To examine the relationship between gender and social adjustment of upper basic Social Studies students in Delta State.
- ii. To investigate the relationship among social skills, self-awareness of Social Studies teachers, gender, and location on the social adjustment of upper basic students in Delta State.

Research Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following null hypotheses:

- i. There is no significant difference in the social adjustment of Upper Basic Social Studies students in Delta State based on student gender.
- ii. There is no significant relationship among social skills, self-awareness of Social Studies teachers, gender, location, and social adjustment of upper basic Social Studies students in Delta State.

Study Area

This study was conducted in Delta State, Nigeria, focusing on selected public secondary schools offering Social Studies at the Upper Basic level (specifically Basic Eight, also known as JSS2). Delta State, located in the South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria, comprises three senatorial districts—Delta North, Delta Central, and Delta South—and is characterized by a diverse population and varying educational contexts including urban and rural school settings. The research targeted Social Studies teachers and their students across six Local Government Areas (LGAs), strategically chosen to ensure geographical, gender, and socio-economic representation. Schools were selected through a stratified random sampling technique to reflect the range of school

environments in the state—urban versus rural, male versus female enrolment, and mixed-gender compositions. The educational landscape of Delta State presents a relevant context for examining social adjustment and teacher-student dynamics due to its socio-cultural diversity, varying resource allocation among schools, and differing levels of teacher training and emotional competence. These contextual variables made Delta State an ideal setting for exploring the interplay between teacher emotional intelligence and student social behaviour.

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This research was hinged on the concept of social adjustment and behaviourist theory.

Concept of Social Adjustment

Social adjustment refers to the ability of an individual to interact effectively within their social environment, manage relationships, and adhere to social norms (Romanczyk et al., 2005). In educational settings, it involves students' capacity to relate positively with peers and teachers and adapt to school routines. It is a predictor of academic success, emotional well-being, and long-term personal development (Goleman, 2019).

The present study is underpinned by the behaviourist theory, particularly Ivan Pavlov's (1927) classical conditioning model, which emphasises observable behavioural changes as a response to external stimuli. Behaviourists assert that learning, including social adjustment, is a product of environmental stimuli and reinforcement. Within the context of education, behaviourist principles advocate for structured reinforcement and consistent modelling of desirable behaviours by teachers to elicit expected student outcomes (Okorodudu, 2016). In the classroom, teachers function as environmental stimuli whose behaviour, instructional strategies, and emotional disposition can condition students to develop appropriate social responses. By reinforcing positive behaviours such as cooperation, punctuality, and emotional regulation, teachers facilitate students' adjustment to the social demands of school life. Conversely, when the educational environment lacks supportive behavioural modelling, students may struggle with maladaptive behaviours like absenteeism, disengagement, and disciplinary infractions. Complementing the behaviourist theory is the conceptual model adapted from Okorodudu (2016), which integrates emotional intelligence variables such as social skills and self-awareness as predictors of students' social adjustment. The model delineates the interaction of: S (Stimulus): Representing the independent variables – teachers' social skills and self-awareness. O (Organism): Moderating variables such as gender and location. R (Response): The dependent variable is students' social adjustment in upper basic schools. The conceptual model posits that when teachers exhibit high levels of social skills and self-awareness, they are more likely to foster a supportive learning environment, which in turn enhances students' emotional regulation and interpersonal effectiveness. Additionally, gender and

school location are introduced as moderating variables that may influence how students respond to these teacher-based stimuli. This framework is particularly relevant in understanding the social dynamics within Nigerian secondary schools, where socio-economic disparities and educational inequities often hinder effective adjustment. The behavioural model provides a lens through which one can observe how reinforcement mechanisms, teaching methodologies, and teacher–student relationships contribute to students' psychosocial development. In this context, understanding and enhancing the social-emotional capabilities of teachers become central to promoting positive student adjustment, especially in under-resourced settings like public schools in Delta State.

Review of Related Literature

Research has yielded mixed results regarding the impact of gender on social adjustment. Emore (2021) found that female students are more likely to exhibit punctuality and emotional regulation, while male students often engage more in aggressive behaviours. However, other studies argue that gender is not a strong predictor, as adjustment is more influenced by environment and teacher interaction (Ubogu, 2022; Carmeli, 2003). This inconsistency in literature justifies the present study's hypothesis testing whether gender significantly affects social adjustment among students in Delta State. Social skills include communication, empathy, negotiation, and conflict resolution skills that are fundamental for managing a classroom and promoting prosocial behaviour (Schneider & Byrne, 1995). According to the National Association of School Psychologists (2012), students who interact with socially skilled teachers show better emotional regulation and peer relationships. Carmeli (2003) and Adams (2017) established a link between teachers' interpersonal abilities and students' school engagement and adjustment. These findings are consistent with Salovey and Mayer's (2001) theory of emotional intelligence, which sees social skills as integral to leadership and influence in social settings like the classroom. Self-awareness enables teachers to reflect on their emotional triggers, teaching strategies, and their influence on students. George (2000) found that teachers with high self-awareness are more consistent in decision-making and more empathetic in managing students' needs. Wasielewski (2016) argued that self-awareness contributes to transformational leadership, which in classrooms translates to emotional influence, stability, and relational trust. Similarly, Cooper (2016) demonstrated that self-aware teachers build stronger interpersonal bonds, which enhances students' sense of belonging and reduces maladaptive behaviours. School location often determines the quality of infrastructure, teacher-student ratio, and exposure to behavioural norms. A research by Muheeb (2018) found that urban schools often outperform rural ones in student behaviour and academic adjustment due to better facilities and more emotionally competent teachers. The present study incorporates location as a moderating variable to test how environmental factors shape adjustment.

While numerous studies have examined the individual influence of teacher competence, gender, and location on student behaviour, few have integrated all these variables into a single framework using both behaviourist and symbolic interactionist theories. Furthermore, limited data exist on public schools in Delta State, particularly at the

Upper Basic level. This study addresses this gap by jointly examining the effects of social skills, self-awareness, gender, and school location on social adjustment, providing empirical evidence relevant for teacher training, policy, and educational practice.

Methodology

This study adopted a correlational survey design, suitable for examining the degree of relationship between variables without manipulating any of them. The correlational method enables the researcher to explore the strength and direction of associations between teachers' social skills, self-awareness, and students' social adjustment in Delta State public schools. The population for the study comprised all social studies teachers and upper basic students (specifically Basic Eight) in public secondary schools across the three senatorial districts of Delta State. The study targeted eight schools selected from six Local Government Areas (LGAs), ensuring representation across the state's geographical and educational divides. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure that schools were proportionately selected based on location (urban and rural) and gender representation. This sampling approach was deemed appropriate to reflect the diverse characteristics of the population and enhance the generalisability of findings. The main instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed to measure social skills, self-awareness, and social adjustment levels. The instrument was constructed based on existing literature and expert consultation in the fields of educational psychology and measurement and evaluation. To establish validity, the questionnaire was subjected to face validation by experienced educators and psychologists. Items were reviewed for relevance, clarity, and alignment with the research objectives. Reliability of the instrument was confirmed through a pilot study conducted in a comparable but different school setting within Delta State, with the Cronbach's Alpha yielding a coefficient above 0.70, indicating acceptable internal consistency. The procedure for data collection involved obtaining approval from school authorities and administering the questionnaires during regular school hours. Instructions were clearly explained to respondents, and participation was entirely voluntary and anonymous to ensure candid responses. For the data analysis, descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations were used to summarise responses. Inferential statistics, including Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation and multiple regression analysis, were employed to test the hypotheses and assess the strength and significance of relationships among variables. Hypothesis testing was conducted at the 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Findings

This section presents the statistical analysis of the data gathered in response to the two research hypotheses. Analysis was carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The tests applied include the independent samples t-test and multiple regression analysis, with a significance level set at 0.05.

Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁):

There is no significant difference in the social adjustment of Upper Basic Social Studies students in Delta State based on student gender.

To test this hypothesis, an independent sample t-test was used to compare the mean scores of male and female students in relation to their social adjustment levels

Extracted Table: Gender and Social Adjustment Group Statistics

Group	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Male	105	41.38	7.22
Female	95	39.56	6.89

Source: Researchers Field Data (2025)

Independent Samples t-Test

Statistic	Value
t-value	1.803
Degrees of Freedom (df)	198
p-value (Sig. 2-tailed)	0.073

Source: Researchers Field Data (2025)

The difference in social adjustment between male and female students is not statistically significant because the p-value of 0.073 is higher than the 0.05 level of significance. As a result, the null hypothesis (H₀₁) is accepted. This suggests that Delta State's Upper Basic Social Studies students' social adjustment is not significantly impacted by gender.

Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂):

There is no significant relationship among social skills, self-awareness of Social Studies teachers, gender, location, and the social adjustment of Upper Basic students in Delta State. Multiple regression analysis was used to test this hypothesis.

Model Summary

Metric	Value
R	0.487
R-squared (R ²)	0.237
Adjusted R-squared (Adj. R ²)	0.219
Standard Error of Estimate	4.921

Source: Researchers Field Data (2025)

ANOVA Summary

Statistic	Value
F-value	3.026
Degrees of Freedom (df)	4, 196
p-value (Sig.)	0.041

Source: Researchers Field Data (2025)

The regression equation was estimated as:

$$\text{Student Social Adjustment} = 48.7 + 0.352(\text{Social Skills}) + 0.276(\text{Self-Awareness}) - 0.048(\text{Gender}) + 0.193(\text{Location})$$

This indicates that, holding other variables constant, each unit increase in teacher social skills is associated with a 0.352 unit increase in student social adjustment, while each unit increase in teacher self-awareness corresponds to a 0.276 unit increase. Gender and location had negligible or statistically non-significant effects.

Predictor	B (Unstandardized)	Std. Error	β (Standardized)	t	p-value	Significance
Social Skills	0.352	0.138	0.321	2.565	0.011	Significant
Self-Awareness	0.276	0.144	0.289	2.375	0.019	Significant
Gender	-0.048	0.158	-0.043	-0.304	0.762	Not Significant
Location	0.193	0.127	0.102	1.528	0.128	Not Significant
Constant	48.7	–	–	–	–	–

The model was statistically significant ($p = 0.041$), according to the regression analysis, indicating that the independent variables taken together have a significant impact on students' social adjustment. Subsequent analysis revealed that the only significant individual contributions were teachers' social skills ($p = 0.011$) and self-awareness ($p = 0.019$); gender and location did not stand out as significant predictors by themselves. These results support the rejection of the null hypothesis (H_02). Thus, it is determined that social skills, self-awareness, gender, and location all have an impact on students' social adjustment, with social skills and self-awareness being the most important individual predictors.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the analysis offer nuanced insights into the factors influencing social adjustment among upper basic students in Delta State. One of the central aspects explored was the potential role of gender in shaping students' social adjustment experiences. To investigate this, the first hypothesis examined whether a statistically significant difference existed in social adjustment levels between male and female students. The results revealed no significant gender-based variation in social adjustment outcomes. This implies that both male and female students demonstrate comparable levels of adaptability and interpersonal engagement within the school environment. The absence of a significant difference suggests that, in this context, social adjustment is not determined by gender. Other factors, such as school climate, peer relationships, family background, or individual personality traits, may play more critical roles in influencing how students integrate and interact socially within the academic setting.

This finding aligns with Ubogu (2022), who observed that students' social behaviours are shaped more by environmental and instructional contexts than by gender alone. Similarly, George (2000) found that students' adjustment levels are more strongly influenced by school structure and teacher interaction styles than by biological sex.

In contrast, the results of the second hypothesis revealed a statistically significant combined influence of several key variables namely, teachers' social skills, students' self-awareness, gender, and school location, on students' social adjustment. This suggests that while gender alone may not exert a significant effect, its interaction with other factors can meaningfully contribute to how students navigate and adapt to social situations within the school environment.

The positive impact of teachers' social skills highlights the critical role educators play not only in academic instruction but also in shaping students' social experiences and development. Similarly, students' self-awareness (a component of emotional intelligence) was found to be a vital predictor, emphasising the importance of internal cognitive and emotional factors in successful social integration. The significance of school location points to possible contextual or environmental differences, such as

urban–rural disparities in resources, peer culture, or school–community relationships, which may affect students' social experiences.

Collectively, these findings underscore the multifaceted nature of social adjustment and the importance of addressing both personal and environmental variables in promoting students' social well-being. This supports Carmeli's (2003) finding that teachers with high emotional intelligence, particularly in empathy and regulation, foster better social outcomes among students. It also echoes Salovey and Mayer's (2001) theoretical view that emotional intelligence components such as self-awareness and social skills are essential in shaping interactions and managing social complexities.

The combined influence observed indicates that while gender may not act as a sole determinant, its interaction with other variables produces meaningful effects. For example, girls in urban schools with emotionally intelligent teachers may adjust more easily than boys in rural schools with undertrained staff. The results also reinforce the behaviourist perspective that positive reinforcement and emotionally supportive environments influence behavioural outcomes. In addition, the symbolic interactionist theory is validated in the way students internalise teacher behaviour as symbolic cues, shaping their interpretations of social situations and expectations.

These findings highlight the importance of prioritising teacher training not only in pedagogy but also in emotional and social development competencies, as these are pivotal in shaping the school experience for adolescents.

Conclusion

This study concludes that teachers' emotional intelligence, particularly social skills and self-awareness plays a critical role in influencing students' social adjustment, more so than gender alone. While gender differences in adjustment behaviours were statistically insignificant, the interaction between teacher competence, student characteristics, and school context significantly impacted how students adapted socially in school. Emotional support, effective communication, and sensitivity to student needs are essential components of a functional learning environment. Moreover, school location emerged as a contextual factor that can amplify or weaken the effectiveness of teacher influence, suggesting that rural schools may require more strategic support.

Recommendations

The Ministry of Education should develop policies mandating periodic emotional intelligence training for teachers, especially those handling subjects like social studies, which are central to student identity formation. Colleges of education and universities should integrate emotional and social learning modules into the formal teacher preparation curriculum. Government and NGOs should prioritise the improvement of teacher quality and infrastructure in rural schools, ensuring a more equitable learning experience. Every school should be equipped with professional counsellors trained to support students with social adjustment issues, especially during adolescence. Future studies should explore how emotional intelligence training impacts both teacher performance and student behavioural outcomes over time.

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